

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Guidance and counseling and career development in some selected secondary schools in Kaduna metropolis

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Abstract

The study explores the instrumentality of Guidance and Counseling as a tool for career development among students of some selected secondary schools in Kaduna metropolis. Through integration of psychological insights into counseling practices, addressing some fundamental and complex questions of career choices and developments, among the targeted population, has been made possible. A survey research has been used, under which some senior and Junior Secondary Schools, with organized system of Guidance and Counseling services, were identified and purposively selected. Simple random sampling technique was employed to select a set of students who must have had number of encounters with their respective school guidance counselors, at different stages of organized programs. With the use of questionnaire as the instrument of data collection, the information obtained were analyzed by means of frequency tables and percentages. Having used chi-square statistics to test the research hypotheses, the findings of the study indicate that, due to the inadequacy of guidance and Counseling services in the area studied, and that where they are available students' career choices and development were majorly guided by the prestige and the pay packages relative to different professions, family remains the dominant source of career information among others. Some useful recommendations have been provided therein.

Keywords: Guidance and Counseling; Career Choices; Secondary Schools; Kaduna-Nigeria

1. Introduction

"The choice of a career is one of the most important decisions one makes in life, It is perhaps as important as the choice of a life partner because its consequences are far reaching" - Ofoegbu (1984). There is no doubt about the truth of the above assertion. However, experience has shown that the process of choosing a career has not always been approached with the seriousness it demands.

How suitable a career, is determined by the amount of satisfaction one will experience in the career and the opportunities one has for advancement. Norman (1963) pointed out that one's choice of career determines the people with whom he will associate with, as well as his place of residence; he also noted that it equally affects one's interests and values. Okediji (1973) quoted by Ofoegbu (1984) also attested to the importance of a good career. The emphasis laid on career counseling by the federal Government in the Nigerian National policy on Education equally underscores the importance of choosing a suitable career in Nigeria.

Due to the importance of career some researchers took it upon themselves to investigate various issues relating to the career development of secondary school students. Achebe (1972), Olayinka (1973), Oluigbo (1976). Ofoegbu (1984). Odo (1988) in their various research work observed that the career of secondary school students in Nigeria have tended

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to be limited to a few materially rewarding profession like law, Medicine, Engineering and Nursing when they could have chosen many more. Olayinka (1973) revealed that the pattern of career choice of students is at times unrealistic. The common experience of teachers when students approach them for assistance in completing their entry forms into higher institutions of learning corroborates this revelation.

Due to the importance of career, it is very necessary that qualitative career education should precede career development. A career should be based on the interest and capability of an individual.

In the past, career education was virtually absent in Nigerian schools. Those who made suitable career decisions were able 'to do so either by accident or because they had older relations and friends who were able to fill the empty space of a career counselor.

Today there has been an improvement on the past. Paid school career counselors are now posted to schools as full time counselors; Career workshop are held intermittently both for the Guidance Counselors and students; Career information or guide are now carefully fitted into various radio programs; and even the federal Government now affect scholarships for those wishing to study Guidance and Counseling.

The question however is, to what extent have all these developments been helpful in enabling students to make more mature and realistic choices of career? The researchers' experience as a teacher counselor is that, up till now, most students still aspire to certain jobs out of fantasy, peer influence, family pressure and enviousness. Such a situation is indeed regrettable and it's what's motivating this research. Guidance and counseling is less reviewed when it comes to research on career development and it's one of the basic factor in career development that is more or less left out in career development and in schools, despite its great importance.

Career as used in the field of counseling has a broad and technical meaning. Technically, it refers to sequence of role or a position including works, leisure and educational pursuit that may encompass a number of occupations, vocations or jobs one engages in during his working life (Seligman, 1980). According to the international Encyclopedia Britannica (1978) career is job for which it is possible to advance during their working life, so that they may get greater responsibility and earn more money.

Career can also be said to be the total lifelong experience of work that has come to serve as a means of earning a livelihood (Kolo, 1991). The career choice previously was not as difficult as it is today. There were fewer job opportunities and more importantly, parents, teachers and religious bodies were aware of the existing opportunities as well as requirements for entry into them. Today, the situation differs for the fact that secondary school students hardly have full knowledge of the requirement for each job and can no longer keep track with the numerous career opportunities, it is against this background that guidance and counseling was introduced to assist the secondary students in choosing a career.

Guidance and counseling is an helping profession which is concerned with molding, reconstructing and rehabilitating a troubled person. It is a self-revealing relationship and both preventive and curative of maladaptive behavior. It is globally accepted that, guidance and counseling activities are for human beings, those with or without problems, normal and abnormal.

The establishment of modern guidance and counseling in secondary schools in Nigeria however, rest on the realization of the need for more sophisticated and integrated package to help individual satisfy their problems and concerns of present day living.

Okon (1984) defined guidance as total program of several highly specialized activities implemented by specialist to help individual make wise and intelligent choice and decisions, counseling on the other hand, has been defined by Makinde (1987) as a service designed to help an individual analyze himself by capabilities, achievements, interest mode of adjustment towards what new decision he has made or has make.

Therefore, since guidance and counseling is a profession, for effective counseling to take place it must involve the application of basic principles for effective helping. These however, include the principle of understanding, sequential process; appreciate self-disclosure and observance of ethics. Their applications not only make counseling effective but also add to the specialist of the counseling relationship.

For guidance to be meaningful, it, must be seen as a series of programmed activities which help the normal school child to know himself/herself as an individual, become more aware of his/her person, experience his/her world and those

people he/she relate with, it is a dynamic process which undergoes continuous change over time as it is not a single event but a series of events, steps or action which are geared towards the general development of the individual. Hence, guidance and counseling play a vital role in the career development of the students.

Objectives of the Study

- To explore the factors influencing career development.
- To find out the role of guidance and counseling in schools.
- To discover the students' sources of career information.

2. Methodology

The location of the study is Kaduna North Local Government Area of Kaduna State, Located in Northwestern Geopolitical zone in Nigeria. The state occupies approximately 48,473.3 square kilometers with an estimated population with three senatorial zones, Southern, Central and Northern senatorial zones. (NPC.gov.ng/2013; NPC. 2006).

Survey research has been used, under which some senior and junior secondary schools, with organized system of Guidance and Counseling services, were identified and purposively selected. For the purpose of this work the study selected four schools, two government and two private schools, out of which 200 respondents were administered questionnaires by means of which information, for analysis in the study, were obtained. Simple random sampling technique was employed to select a set of students who must have had a number of encounter with their respective school guidance counselors, at different stages of organized programs. In co-educational schools that is, Rimi College Ungwan rimi Kaduna, 80 questionnaires were administered. In Government Girls Secondary School Independence way Kaduna, 60 questionnaires have been administered. In Universal Academy Ungwan Rimi, and Hampos International Secondary School Kaduna, 60 Questionnaires have been administered each. In all the schools 200 questionnaires were administered. The data obtained from the survey instrument were analyzed by means of frequency tables and percentages. With the use of chi-square statistics, the research hypotheses were tested to establish the extent to which the variables in question are related.

2.1. Results and Discussions of Research Findings

This section presents the analysis of data collected. The Tables show the results of data collected in respect of the research objectives. And it's presented in percentages.

Table 1 Factors responsible for the student's career development

S/n	Factors	Yes		No	
		No.	%	No.	%
1	Parents Opinion	160	80	40	20
2	Other members of the Family	134	67	66	33
3	Models	38	19	162	81
4	Guidance Counselor	52	26	148	74
5	Principal/Teachers	14	7	186	93
6	Country's present needs	126	63	74	37
7	Service to others	150	75	50	25
8	Low cost of Training	13	6.5	187	93.5
9	Prestige in the Job	187	93.5	13	6.5
10	High Salary	186	93	17	7

Source: Survey 2023

Table 2 Response to the “others” category

S/n	Factors	No. of Students	Percentage (%)
1	Interest in the Job	168	84
2	Friends	58	29
3	Aptitude in Related Subjects	133	66.5

Source: Survey 2023

Table 3 The roles of guidance and counseling in schools

S/n	Schools	Yes		No	
		No.	%	No.	%
1	Rimi College Ungwan rimi Kaduna	33	41.3	47	58.7
2	Government Girls Secondary School Independence way Kaduna	22	36.7	38	63.3
3	Hamos International Secondary School Kaduna	25	83.3	5	16.7

Source: Survey 2023

Table 4 The sources of career information available to the students

S/n	Source of Career Information	No. of Students who Choose each Source	Percentage of students (%)
1	Teacher	6	3
2	Principal	2	1
3	Family	66	33
4	Magazines	8	4
5	Career Books	22	11
6	Radio	6	3
7	Films	3	1.5
8	Friends	25	12.5
9	Guidance Counselor/ Career Master	16	8
10	Previous work Experience	2	1
11	Government Gazette/ Publications	14	7
12	Lecture	19	9.5
13	School Activities	7	3.5
14	Others	4	2
	Total	200	100

Source: Survey 2023

Table 5 Analysis of Hypothesis

School	Yes	No	Total
Rimi college	33	47	80
G.G.S.S Independence way	22	38	60
Hamos International	25	5	30
Total	80	90	170

Source: Survey 2023

- **H1** The calculated Chi Square of 19.52 at the alpha level of 0.05 and the Df of 2 is higher than the critical value of 5.991 therefore the alternate hypothesis shows there is a significant relationship between the role of guidance and counseling and students career development.
- **H2** The calculated Chi Square of 19.52 at the alpha level of 0.05 and the Df of 2 is higher than the critical value of 5.991 therefore the null hypothesis is rejected there is significant relationship between guidance and counseling and students.

3. Discussion and Interpretation of Results

The discussions and interpretations of data are presented under the following headings:

Factors influencing students career decision, Roles of Guidance and counseling and Sources of career information available to the students.

3.1. Factors responsible for student's career development;

Table 1 and 2; show the summary of students' responses in respect of the factors affecting their career decisions. The scores of each factor and those mentioned in the "others" category are shown in these tables.

In descending order of magnitude, prestige and high salary took the first and second positions with 93.5% and 93% respectively. That the students responded positively in great number to these factors corroborates what has been said in the literature review that the student's choice of career is more often than not determined by materialistic considerations such as high pay and prestige.

Coming next as a factor responsible for the career development of students is parent's opinion, scoring 80% and coming third. Fourth and fifth respectively are service to others with 75% and other members of the family with 67%. This shows that in spite of the student's materialistic tendencies, they still tune their minds to more noble drives like service to others. The country's present needs ranked sixth with a pass mark of 63%

Factors which did not score up to 40% and therefore cannot be regarded as major factors responsible for the career development of students are: Guidance counselors 26% (7th) Models 19% (8th) Principals and teachers 7% (9th) and low cost of training 5% (10th).

As a sociologist the researcher is not happy that guidance and counselors are yet to be in the center of activity among students in respect of their career decision as they are supposed to, as it is their function.

3.2. Roles of guidance and counseling;

Table 3 shows that out of the four (4) schools selected not all have an erected guidance and counseling service as the ratio is 3:1 Universal academy do not have while the other three (3) Rimi College, Government Girls Secondary School and Hamos has. Meaning that not all secondary schools in Kaduna north metropolis has a guidance counseling services not to talk of performing its roles which is very essential to students career development and personality build up also.

Table 4 shows how effective guidance and counseling has been performing their roles in the schools since it was established, the summary is 40% to 60% put all together the three (3) schools. 40 said Yes and 60 said No so 40% of the students agreed guidance and counseling officials performed their roles from personal experience and 60% said the guidance and counseling are not performing their roles. Which means that even in schools where the service is present it is still not that effective in the operation of its roles to the students.

Though Hampos international show modest result with 83.3% Yes and a 16.7 No which shows good commitment of the body in performing its roles in that school this shows that there are other schools that the body is very effective and fully implemented but the counts won't be encouraging which shows that when fully implemented the guidance and counseling will be effective in performing its roles. While the other two (2) schools had a result of below average, Rimi college with 41.3% Yes and Government Girls Secondary School with 36.7 Yes.

3.3. Sources of career information available to students

In rank order, the family took the highest frequency with 33%, as a source of career information for the students (see table 5) this was equally the case in the studies carried out by Ofoegbu (1984) and Emezue (1977). The researcher joins Ofoegbu (1984) in her view on this situation. According to her, it is not surprising that the family was identified as the student's major source of job information, considering the strong family ties found in Nigeria. In this type of relationship, the parents may use their children to fulfill their cherished life work which they could not attain by influencing the career aspirations of their children.

Coming next to family as a source of career information is 'Friends' with 12.5%. 'This situation is deplorable because it is one of the root causes of unrealistic career decisions among our youths.

Career books with 11%, lecture with 9.5% and Guidance counselor/ Career masters with 8% took the third, fourth and fifth positions respectively. This shows that some of the students are aware of the availability; of career books and are as well benefiting from the lectures delivered at various career days/workshops and other activities in the Guidance and Counseling program. However, that is only 8% of students representing the total study sample mentioned.

Guidance counselor /career master is an indication that most students are yet to benefit from all the facets of the guidance and counseling program in schools.

Government Gazette/publication accounted for 7% of the total responses, ranking 6th while magazines with 4% and school activities with 3% ranked 7th and 8th respectively.

Radio and teachers ranked 9th with 3% each. Others have ranked 11 with 2% and films ranked 12th with 1.5% while previous work experience ranked 13th with 1%, and principal with 1% also. That these two came last is not surprising since the bad state of the economy no longer allows youngsters the opportunity to undertake part time jobs during long vacations.

Secondly the work load on the principal makes him inaccessible to the students for matters not bordering on school administration. In the work of Achebe (1972) only 0.5 % of the students she worked with chose the principal as their source of job information while in that of Ofoegbu (1984) none of the students identified the principal as a source of job information. Sources mentioned in the 'Others' category include newspaper advertisements, interests, novels and Joint Admission & Matriculation Board' Brochure.

3.4. Implications and Recommendations of the Study

The findings of this study have implications for Federal Ministry of Education, Curriculum Planners and Guidance Counselors in secondary schools.

It has been discovered that students have a parochial occupational horizon and that their occupational aspirations do not derive from appropriate source of career information. To curb these problems, the federal ministry of education should see to it that all State ministries of education work to ensure that all schools have strong Guidance Counseling unit. Currently not all the schools in Kaduna north have Guidance Counselor.

More so, National Curriculum Planners and makers of National Policy on education should make it mandatory that Guidance and Counseling program, be established at the primary school level. This will help in creating early awareness among pupils about the benefits of Guidance and Counseling services especially in career decisions.

While the appointment of Guidance counselor for all schools and the establishment of Guidance services at the primary school level are being recommended, the researcher is also advising that all practicing, Guidance Counselors should strengthen efforts to redirect the students minds to better source of career information and factors that should inform their career decisions. They should also work to broaden the student's career horizon.

The counselors can achieve these by organizing career weeks more frequently and by forming career clubs in schools.

Recommendations made are:

- The State Education Commission should ensure posting/placements of Guidance Counselor in schools.
- The same body should sponsor career workshop as this will help widen student's career horizon.
- Guidance Counselors posted should also ensure that enough occupational information is collected for display on bulletin boards.

3.5. Suggestion for Further Research:

Another area that further research could be done on is the place of career masters and the effectiveness of career counseling among secondary school students. This study was done in Kaduna north local government area of Kaduna state; it will be interesting to carry out the study in other zones to know whether the results will correlate.

3.5.1. Summary of the Study:

The study set out to investigate the issue of Guidance and Counseling and Career Development in some selected secondary schools in Kaduna North Local Government area. The objectives of this study were: To explore the factors influencing career development; To find out the role of Guidance and Counseling in Schools; To discover the students' sources of career information.

To guide the study, three research questions were formulated.

A total of 200 secondary school students from Kaduna north local government from four (4) different schools were used for the study.

Questionnaire was the instrument used for the study. Percentages were used in the analysis of data and Chi Square for testing Hypothesis.

3.5.2. The findings showed that

- Materialistic consideration was the major factors that influenced the student's career decisions. In rank order 'Prestige' and 'High Salary' took the first and the second positions respectively. Parent's opinion came third.
- Because of the inadequacy of and in some cases absence of Guidance and Counseling services, the students' career horizon is poor and the career chosen were mainly high status careers.
- The family was the major source of career information used by the students. Friends' and career books came second and third, in rank order.

This research was sectioned into five chapters, chapter one contains background of the study, statement of the problem, objectives of the study, research question, scope and delimitation, significance of the study, definition of terms.

Chapter two is review of related literature where we looked at the various works done by other scholars which are directly or indirectly related to this work and theoretical framework where career theories were reviewed.

Chapter three is research Location, Population of the study, Types and Sources of Data, Validity and Reliability of the Research Instrument, Method of Data Collection, Sample Size and Sampling Technique, Administration of the Instrument, Method of Data Analysis, and Limitation of the Study.

Chapter four contains presentation and analysis of data, discussion and interpretation of results.

Chapter five entails the implication and recommendation of the study, suggestion for further research, summary of the study.

Compliance with ethical standards

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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